

IMAGINE THERE'S PHILAEENUS SPUMARIUS CONTROL

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Insect vectors of plant microorganism are primary targets of insect-borne pathogens control. Evidence about the vector role of *Philaenus spumarius* (L.) (Hemiptera Aphrophoridae) (*Ps*) in transmitting *Xylella fastidiosa* Wells, Raju *et al.* subsp. *pauca* OQDS strain (*Xf*), makes the control of this species of major importance. Data about vector life cycle, behaviour, population dynamics and bionomics are needed to design IPM control strategies (focused on the prevention of plant pathogen transmission) for both Integrated or Organic farming. *Ps* has an univoltine life cycle, it overwinters as an egg, nymphs develop in spring and female adults undergo a summer ovaric diapause. In OQDS and adjacent areas, the egg hatching occurs during the end of February and March. Juveniles live on herbs and bush twigs in "spittle" made purposely frothing mucus and faeces. *Philaenus spumarius* adults are active from May to December. Newly-hatched nymphs are gregarious but shift to solitary later in their development. Adults are food search-driven in their mass movements and shift from host to host following sap availability. The population is at maximum as eggs, and it decreases during pre-imaginal life-stages for several, not yet perfectly known mortality factors. Adults are still abundant in fall when they start to lay eggs. Population drops down almost to zero in middle November, but rare individuals are still active in middle December. In OQDS habitats, a mass movement from drying herbs to olive trees occurs around flowering time, and results in *Xf* acquisition from infected plants and subsequent new infections. We figure a *Ps* integrated control based on two control actions, namely a) mechanical control of nymphs and b) chemical control of adults. Careful timing both control actions is of paramount importance. We consider nymph control the key control action while adult control either may be a supplementary action in case of high vector population or in case of ineffective control of juveniles. In organic farming, only mechanical control of immatures can be applied. Unfortunately, we have no fully effective insecticides, or further control means options, by the time. Despite pyrethroids or Sweet Orange Essential Oil appear somewhat effective against the adult spittlebugs, their negatively impact on the olive biocenosis because they are broad spectrum. Finally, we are developing our index of impact for vector control actions based on Regione Puglia land use stats and willing to share and discuss the impact of control options with PONTE stakeholders.